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TERRITORIAL DIFFERENCES IN THE LEXICAL-SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF OIKONYMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

Abstract. *The article studies the lexical and semantic typology of oikonyms of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in connection with which, at the first stage of the work, research works devoted to the semantic classification of geographical names were analyzed. The authors of the article subdivided the oikonyms of the Republic of Karakalpakstan into 16 lexical and semantic groups: oikonyms associated with the features of the geographical location; oikonyms associated with the features of the relief; oikonyms formed from oronyms; oikonyms associated with the features of the soil; oikonyms formed from hydronyms; phytooikonyms; zooikonyms; ethnooikonyms; anthrooikonyms; oikonyms associated with professions and areas of economic activity; oikonyms associated with household and farm buildings; oikonyms formed from historical terms; mythical oikonyms; strange names; migration oikonyms (displaced names); modern (standard) names. Based on statistical analysis by regions of the republic, territorial differences in the etymology of oikonyms were identified and a map of the lexical-semantic structure of oikonymy of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was compiled.*

Key words: *toponym, oikonym, hydronym, oronym, ethnonym, phytonym, anthroponym, zoonym, lexical-semantic, classification.*

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ТЕРРИТОРИАЛЬНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ В ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОЙ СТРУКТУРЕ ОЙКОНИМОВ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН

Аннотация. *В статье исследована лексико-семантическая типология ойконимов Республики Каракалпакстан, в связи с чем на первом этапе работы проанализированы исследовательские работы, посвящённые смысловой классификации географических названий. Авторами статьи ойконимы Республики Каракалпакстан подразделены на 16 лексико-семантических групп: ойконимы, связанные с особенностями географического положения; ойконимы, связанные с особенностями рельефа; ойконимы, образованные от оронимов; ойконимы, связанные с особенностями почвы; ойконимы, образованные от гидронимов; фитоойконимы; зоойконимы; этноойконимы; антропоойконимы; ойконимы, связанные с профессиями и направлениями хозяйственной деятельности; ойконимы, связанные с домашними и хозяйственными постройками; ойконимы, образованные от исторических терминов; мифические ойконимы; странные названия; миграционные ойконимы (перемещённые названия); современные (стандартные) названия. На основе статистического анализа по районам республики выявлены территориальные различия в этимологии ойконимов и составлена карта лексико-семантической структуры ойконимии Республики Каракалпакстан.*

Ключевые слова: *топоним, ойконим, гидроним, ороним, этноним, фитоним, антропоим, зооним, лексик-семантик, классификация.*

Introduction and problem statement. Due to the fact that human production, economic and social activity is carried out within the framework of a geographical environment consisting of many objects with their own names, the names of geographical objects always serve as addresses, there was no socio-economic formation without geographical names. Geographical names, as a direct symbol of history, are constantly supplemented, renamed, and updated due to the way of life of peoples who have lived there for centuries, serving the various

needs of society. At the same time, geographical names show the diversity of the surrounding natural environment, the presence of natural resources, the diversity of landscapes, climatic and hydrographic, relief and orographic features, as well as the appearance, location and other important features and signs of natural and other objects. In general, geographical names are often considered a source of various information. Therefore, the study of geographical names, their scientific research, the etymology of each place name, and the determination of its meaning are of paramount importance. This research covers the toponyms of the settlements in the Republic of Karakalpakstan according to the decrees on administrative and territorial division of the Presidium of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and District Councils of People's deputies as of January 1, 2021. According to these official documents the Republic had 12 cities, 26 townships (settlements) and 1113 localities, i.e., all in all there were 1151 localities as of January 1, 2021, [5]. The article determines the number of administrative-territorial units of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the lexical and semantic features (etymology) of its oikonyms based on the total number of settlements given in the above-mentioned documents.

Study of the problem. Many geographers have contributed to the scientific, theoretical and practical development of the science of toponymy. A number of foreign and local geographers have conducted numerous scientific studies on the lexical-semantic typology of toponyms and place names of different regions. In particular, geographers such as V.P.Semenov-Tyan-Shansky [22], E.M.Murzaev [19], V.A.Juchkevich [12,13] from the CIS countries and H.H.Hasanov [10], S.K.Karaev [15], P.N.Gulomov [8], M.T.Mirakmalov [18], K.M.Seitniyazov [21], Yu.I.Ahmadaliev [2], K.M.Khakimov [9] from local scientists conducted their research on the lexical-semantic typology of toponyms.

K.Abdimuratov [3,4], S.K.Kamalov [14], Kh.Esbergenov [6], K.M.Seitniyazov [21], D.T.Yuldashev [25], G.M.Abishov [1], I.O.Kholmuratov [17], A.E.Esemuratov [7], J.E.Toreniyazov [23] made a certain contribution to the study of oikonyms in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. However, research conducted to date has not covered all the oikonyms of the republic and has not identified territorial differences in the context of districts. The novelty of this research is that all the oikonyms of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are covered and their lexical-semantic features and territorial differences are determined in the context of the districts.

Aim and objectives of the research. The main goal of the study is to develop a lexical-semantic typology (content) and a map of oikonyms (1151 toponyms) of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The main tasks are to study classifications developed so far by geographical scientists and lexical-semantic type of each toponym on the bases of their etymology.

Materials and methods. During the research, the works of foreign and domestic scientists on the lexical-semantic typology of toponyms were used. In addition, when determining the meanings of oikonyms in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, data identified at meetings with the local population and experts during field research were also used. In addition, toponymical dictionaries, scientific and popular science literature, and materials from the collection of linguistic expeditions were used.

Historical, statistical, cartographic, geographical-typological and desk research methods were also used in the research work.

Results and its discussion. It is obvious that each geographical name is a source of understanding the world, helps to correctly understand humanity, objective events in the geographical environment. Therefore, the secret of each geographical object is accumulated in its name. In order to define the etymology of the name, in the first place, the natural, social, economical, political and linguistic factors should be studied along with the events of the time. If we accept the scientific, political, practical and educational significance of toponyms, then the importance of their study will continue to increase [16, p.172]. The first studies on the classification of geographical names were carried out by V.P.Semenov-Tyan-Shansky. In his work "How the geographical landscape is reflected in folk tales", he laid the foundations for the semantic classification of names in toponymy. V.P.Semenov-Tyan-Shansky divides

settlements into the following seven groups. These are: 1) derived from human names and nicknames (surnames); 2) taken from church holidays; 3) derived from historical names; 4) names associated with ancient beliefs; 5) descended from ancient tribes, Aborigines or colonists of a particular territory; 6) derived from modern names in honor of various phenomena and individuals; 7) derived from the objects that make up or participate in the typical geographical landscape of a given area [22, p.133-158].

E.M.Murzaev classifies toponyms in his work "Geography in names" and divides them into 10 semantic types: [19, p.93-98] 1) names related to specific features of the relief; 2) names related to water objects and their characters; 3) phytotoponyms, names associated with plant species; 4) zootoponyms, names associated with animal species; 5) anthrotoponyms, that is, names given to people's names, surnames, and nicknames; 6) names associated with production; 7) names related to trade and transport; 8) social names; 9) ethnotoponyms, names associated with the names of peoples, seeds and tribes; 10) names that appeared related to ideology and politics.

Within the framework of the semantic classification of toponyms, V.A.Juchkevich [12, p.90] divides toponyms into the following 8 types: 1) names that appeared in connection with the natural conditions of the area (relief, soil, vegetation, water, etc.); 2) names created on the basis of socio-economic phenomena (ethnic composition, labor activity, transport routes, etc.); 3) names describing the properties of the object (its size, age, distinguishing features, etc.); 4) patronymic names (related to people's first and last names); 5) transferred names (names given in imitation of other names); 6) names of religious or legendary significance; 7) memorial and symbolic names; 8) names that are still unclear.

H.H.Hasanov [10, p.26] divided geographical names into the following 10 types: 1) names related to the position, character, surface and climate of the place; 2) hydronyms, names associated with water; 3) names related to plants and animals; 4) names associated with minerals; 5) names related to profession and administration; 6) names associated with people, tribes and seeds; 7) names given to names and surnames of individuals; 8) names of legendary and religious; 9) strange names; 10) new tense names.

S.K.Karaev [15, p.12-18] in his scientific research studies the semantic classification of oikonyms divided into two groups as follows:

1. Oikonyms denoting natural geographical objects.
2. Socio-economic oikonyms.

1. Symbols denoting natural geographical objects include names of water bodies, geomorphological forms of places, flora and fauna, and other natural objects. They are divided into the following types: a) hydrooikonyms – oikonyms associated with any water object; b) oroikonyms – oikonyms related to the forms of the earth's surface, i.e. relief; c) phyto-oikonyms - oikonyms related to plant names; d) zooikonyms – oikonyms related to animal names.

2. Socio-economic oikonyms are oikonyms related to the production and economic activities of people and are divided into the following types: a) antropooikonyms - oikonyms assigned to names and nicknames of people; b) ethnooikonyms - oikonyms derived from the names of different nations; c) oikonyms named according to the types of professions of people; d) trade and transport oikonyms; e) social oikonyms.

In places where the social structure of the population has been preserved, the following oikonyms exist: a) oikonyms formed depending on the standard of living; b) oikonyms formed depending on their social origin; c) ideological names; d) migrooikonyms - oikonyms arising from population migration.

In the semantic classification of geographical names, P.N.Gulomov [8] divided them into three large groups, which in turn were divided into subtypes.

I. Names that originated in connection with the natural characteristics of the place, that is, the geographical objects.

II. Names that appeared in connection with socio-economic, political characteristics and circumstances.

III. Legendary and strange names.

Each large group, in turn, is further divided into separate species.

I. Names that originated in connection with the natural features of the place: a) names related to geographic place features; b) names related to the peculiarity of the place; c) toponyms related to relief features; d) names related to the climate, meteorological elements of the place; e) water related names – hydronyms; f) plants, names associated with their species; g) animals related place names; h) derived toponyms associated with minerals.

II. Names that appeared in connection with socio-economic characteristics, political situations: a) names related to profession and administration; b) historical names related to important events in the history of the country; c) names that originated in connection with a people, clan, tribe, that is, ethnonyms; d) names related to people's names, nicknames, that is, anthroponyms; e) religious names; f) modern names.

III. Legendary and strange names.

K.M.Seitniyazov [21, p.45-64] semantically divided the toponyms of the northern districts of the right bank of Karakalpakstan into the following groups: 1) geographical names, anthropotoponyms formed in connection with a person's name, surname and nickname; 2) geographical names that have arisen depending on the people and their seeds, ethnotoponyms; 3) geographical names associated with people profession; 4) geographical names associated with plants and animals; 5) geographical names that arose with the participation of geographical terms; 6) hydronyms; 7) geographical names formed depending on the location's relief; 8) geographical names associated with the minerals; 9) incomprehensible geographical names.

M.T.Mirakmalov, in his scientific article “Classification of oikonyms of Uzbekistan”, scientifically analysed the oikonyms of Uzbekistan based on the classification of oikonyms by E.M.Murzaev and S.K.Karaev, and noted that the grouped study of oikonyms of Uzbekistan facilitates their assimilation and study [18].

Yu.I.Ahmadaliev, in his work “Toponyms of the Ferghana Region”, semantically divides place names into the following groups:

1. Natural or natural geographic oikonyms.
2. Economic-social oikonyms.

While physical-geographical oikonyms are divided into oikonyms related to water, reflecting the relief, derived from the names of plants and animals, economic-social oikonyms, in turn, are divided into oikonyms derived from people's names, names of tribes, and from the spheres of production and social life. These, in turn, were also divided into subgroups [2, p.24-25].

K.M.Khakimov [9, p.12-13] studied the oikonyms of the Jizzakh region, semantically dividing them into oikonyms formed under the influence of natural and socio-economic factors.

A) Natural or natural geographic oikonyms. They are in turn classified into the following types: hydrooikonym, oroikonym, phytooikonym and zooikonym.

B) socio-economic geographic oikonyms. They are in turn classified into the following types: anthropooikonym, ethnooikonym, oikonyms reflecting economic activity and neoikonyms.

Thus, in the geographical and toponymic literature one can find several varieties of lexical-semantic typology of toponyms. From the above data it is clearly seen that these typologies are in some respects similar to each other and most of the typological groups in them are repeated.

However, during the research process, when all 1151 oikonyms were studied from a lexical-semantic point of view, we found some toponyms with a distinct lexical-semantic meaning and etymology, but which did not correspond to any of the group classifications mentioned above.

Thus, the experiments mentioned in the scientific literature were generalized, and all cases discovered during the research process were taken into account and the following lexical-semantic classification of oikonyms of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was developed [5]:

1. Oikonyms related to geographic place features;
2. Oikonyms related to relief features;
3. Oikonyms formed from oronyms;
4. Oikonyms related to soil features;
5. Oikonyms formed from hydronyms;
6. Phytooikonyms;
7. Zoooikonyms;
8. Ethnooikonyms;
9. Anthropooikonyms;
10. Oikonyms related to profession, household products;
11. Oikonyms related to house and farm buildings;
12. Oikonyms formed from historical terms;
13. Legendary oikonyms;
14. Strange oikonyms;
15. Transferred oikonyms (migrant names);
16. Modern (standart) names.

Of the 1151 oikonyms of Karakalpakstan, most, i.e. 26 percent consists of ethnooikonyms (Figure 1). Ethnooikonyms are especially common in the north-eastern regions of the republic. Firstly, the Karakalpaks gave tribal and clan names to their settlements, lakes and irrigation networks. According to T.A.Jdanko: “The Karakalpak tribes preserved their place of settlement and the integrity of their territory long before the Russian invasion, and, they say, they maintained this in colonial times” [11, p.66]. These opinions are reflected in modern ethnooikonyms, such as Esebiy, Estek, Jamansha, Qatagan, Tamgali, Shuyit and many others.

In the new irrigated territories in Soviet times, new villages were assigned standardized ideological names, but during the period of Independence they were renamed to modern (standard) names, such as Dosliq, Gulistan, Miynetkesh, Abat, Pakhtaabat, Tinishliq, Jasliq, etc. Now such toponyms make up 21,8 percent of the republic’s oikonyms.

When hydronyms become names of settlements, differences arise in the meaning and nature of responsibilities. Therefore, both cases should be taken into account here. If the body of water identified by the hydronym still exists, then the name is well known in the language as a hydronym. Its oikonymic meaning will be secondary. The body of water designated by the hydronym may not exist today, or could disappear after a certain period of time. In such cases, the oikonymic name of the place continues to exist, and not the hydronymic one [20, p.40]. Indeed, one can see many oikonyms derived from hydronyms, but in the region where these oikonyms are located, no water bodies are visible. Examples of them include such oikonyms as Aspantay, Akkul, Pishenkul, Shilimkul, Kungradkul and others. Oikonyms derived from hydronyms make up 15.2% of all oikonyms in the region.

The appearance of anthropooikonyms began to arise during the slave system, when social classes first appeared. During the period of feudalism, based on private property, the main distinguishing feature of a locality was the name of its owner. As a result, villages and hamlets were named after major feudal lords, tribal and social leaders, and local chiefs. This tradition continued till the 20th century. Today, settlements, streets, squares, parks and villages bear the names of famous statesmen, politicians, defenders of the country, labour veterans, scientists and cultural figures, and a new layer of anthropooikonyms is created [20, p.47-48]. In the territory of Karakalpakstan, in many settlements, the names of Aydos, Ajiniyaz, Berdakh, Beruni, Babur, Ernazar, Tolibay Kabulov and other historical figures, politicians, historically famous tribal and public figures have been preserved. They make up 13% of all oikonyms.

Fig. 1. Lexical-semantic groups of oikonyms of the Republic of Karakalpakstan
 The ашигы was made by the authorsю

In ancient times, our ancestors built their villages on hills, thinking more about protection from possible attacks of enemies. This gave them the ability to see enemies at a distance or warn others of danger. Especially in the southern regions of Karakalpakstan, most historical towns were created for the purpose of defence. Although they have now fallen into disuse, they played an important role in the formation of oikonyms. Of all the toponyms in the republic, 6.2% are oikonyms associated with the construction of houses and utility premises. Plants are closely related to the material history of mankind and have played a huge role in the lives and activities of people. Therefore, people began to use the names of various plants as toponyms. A large number of plant names are assigned to the settlements of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, most of the names belong to cultivated plants and cereal plants [24]. Of all oikonyms in the republic, 2.8% are phytooikonyms.

During the research work, the types of lexical-semantic classification of oikonyms in each region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan were studied (table 1, fig. 2).

Ethnooikonyms and antropooikonyms make up the majority of the lexical-semantic composition of oikonyms in the Amudarya district. Since people usually lived along rivers, canals, lakes and other bodies of water, there are many oikonyms derived from hydronyms. Oikonyms such as Wakhim and Yarimshi, derived from historical names relating to the Khanate of Khiva, are still in use.

Most of the oikonyms of the Beruni region are modern (standard) names. This means that a lot of new land has been developed recently. Along with this, the tradition of perpetuating the names of historical figures and preserving the names of former landowners led to the emergence of such anthroponyms as Beruni, Navayi, Babur, Koshkinbay and Nurmanbay and a number of other similar ones.

Hydrooikonyms make up the majority in the Bozatau district. As a result of the shallowing of the Amudarya River, the lakes Aspantay, Shilimkul, Moyinkul, Arpakul, Uygirkul and Kopakkul and others that previously existed in the region dried up and disappeared. Today, the existence of these lakes in the past can be learned from the oikonyms derived from their names.

Table 1

Lexical-semantic composition of oikonyms of administrative-territorial units of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

№	Lexical-semantic groups of oikonyms	Districts and cities								
		Nukus c.	Amudarya	Beruni	Bozatau	Kegeyli	Muynak	Nukus d.	Takhiyatatas	Takhtakupir
1	Oikonyms related to geographic place features	0	8 / 6,2%	0	0	1 / 0,8%	0	1 / 2,5%	0	0
2	Oikonyms related to relief features	0	1 / 0,8%	0	0	2 / 1,5%	0	0	0	2 / 5%
3	Oikonyms formed from oronyms	1 / 50%	2 / 1,6%	3 / 4,2%	2 / 7,7%	1 / 0,8%	4 / 18,2%	2 / 5%	1 / 3,1%	1 / 2,5%
4	Oikonyms related to soil features	0	5 / 3,9%	1 / 1,4%	0	0	0	0	3 / 9,4%	0
5	Oikonyms formed from hydronyms	0	20 / 15,5%	2 / 2,8%	13 / 50%	8 / 6,1%	12 / 54,5%	8 / 20%	7 / 21,9%	15 / 37,5%
6	Phytooikonyms	0	6 / 4,6%	5 / 7,1%	1 / 3,8%	1 / 0,8%	0	2 / 5%	1 / 3,1%	2 / 5%
7	Zoooikonyms	0	2 / 1,5%	1 / 1,4%	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Ethnooikonyms	1 / 50%	25 / 19,4%	3 / 4,2%	4 / 15,4%	83 / 62,8%	0	13 / 32,5%	7 / 21,9%	6 / 15%
9	Anthropooikonyms	0	23 / 17,8%	12 / 16,9%	0	15 / 11,3%	3 / 13,6%	6 / 15%	5 / 15,6%	4 / 10%
10	Oikonyms related to profession, household products	0	7 / 5,45%	1 / 1,4%	0	2 / 1,5%	0	0	0	2 / 5%
11	Oikonyms related to house and farm buildings	0	10 / 7,7%	6 / 8,4%	2 / 7,7%	9 / 6,8%	1 / 4,5%	3 / 7,5%	2 / 6,2%	4 / 10%
12	Oikonyms formed from historical terms	0	4 / 3,1%	1 / 1,4%	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	Legendary oikonyms	0	0	0	0	0	0	1 / 2,5 %	0	0
14	Strange oikonyms	0	0	0	0	1 / 0,8%	0	0	1 / 3,1%	0
15	Transferred oikonyms (migrant names)	0	2 / 1,5%	0	1 / 3,8%	0	1 / 4,5%	1 / 2,5 %	1 / 3,1%	0
16	Modern (standart) names	0	14 / 10,8%	36 / 50,7%	3 / 11,6%	9 / 6,8%	1 / 4,5%	3 / 7,5%	4 / 12,5%	4 / 10%
Total		2 / 100%	129 / 100%	71 / 100%	26 / 100%	132 / 100%	22 / 100%	40 / 100%	32 / 100%	40 / 100%

№	Lexical-semantic groups of oikonyms	Districts and cities								KR
		Turtkul	Khodjeyli	Chimbay	Shumanay	Ellikkala	Kanlikul	Karauzyak	Kungrad	
1	Oikonyms related to geographic place features	4 / 4,3%	1 / 1,6%	0	1 / 0,9%	0	0	2 / 2,1%	1 / 2,1%	19 / 1,7%
2	Oikonyms related to relief features	3 / 3,3%	1 / 1,6%	1 / 0,8%	2 / 1,9%	1 / 1,1%	1 / 2,5%	1 / 1%	0	15 / 1,3%
3	Oikonyms formed from oronyms	3 / 3,3%	3 / 4,6%	1 / 0,8%	1 / 0,9%	1 / 1,1%	1 / 2,5%	6 / 6,2%	1 / 2,1%	34 / 3%
4	Oikonyms related to soil features	3 / 3,3%	0	4 / 3,4%	0	1 / 1,1%	0	0	1 / 2,1%	18 / 1,6%
5	Oikonyms formed from hydronyms	11 / 11,9%	17 / 26,6%	9 / 7,5%	17 / 16,2%	6 / 6,5%	12 / 30,8%	12 / 12,4%	6 / 12,5%	175 / 15,2%
6	Phytooikonyms	5 / 5,4%	1 / 1,6%	1 / 0,8%	1 / 0,95%	2 / 2,2%	0	2 / 2,1%	3 / 6,2%	33 / 2,8%
7	Zoooikonyms	1 / 1,1%	0	0	0	1 / 1,1%	0	1 / 1%	1 / 2,1%	7 / 0,6%
8	Ethnooikonyms	1 / 1,1%	12 / 18,7%	71 / 59,2%	12 / 11,4%	4 / 4,4%	12 / 30,8%	36 / 37,1%	10 / 20,8%	300 / 26%
9	Anthropooikonyms	6 / 6,5%	10 / 15,6%	16 / 13,4%	7 / 6,7%	19 / 20,6%	6 / 15,4%	13 / 13,4%	5 / 10,4%	150 / 13%
10	Oikonyms related to profession, household products	3 / 3,2%	2 / 3,1%	6 / 5%	4 / 3,8%	6 / 6,5%	0	4 / 4,1%	0	37 / 3,2%
11	Oikonyms related to house and farm buildings	5 / 5,4%	5 / 7,8%	3 / 2,5%	3 / 2,9%	10 / 10,8%	3 / 7,7%	4 / 4,1%	1 / 2,1%	71 / 6,2%
12	Oikonyms formed from historical terms	1 / 1,1%	0	2 / 1,6%	0	1 / 1,1%	0	2 / 2,1%	0	11 / 1%
13	Legendary oikonyms	0	1 / 1,6%	0	0	4 / 4,4%	0	0	1 / 2,1%	7 / 0,6%
14	Strange oikonyms	0	0	0	0	1 / 1,1%	0	0	0	3 / 0,3%
15	Transferred oikonyms (migrant names)	4 / 4,3%	1 / 1,6%	1 / 0,8%	1 / 0,9%	1 / 1,1%	0	4 / 4,1%	2 / 4,2%	20 / 1,7%
16	Modern (standart) names	42 / 45,6%	10 / 15,6%	5 / 4,2%	56 / 53,3%	34 / 36,9%	4 / 10,2%	10 / 10,3%	16 / 33,3%	251 / 21,8%
Total		92 / 100%	64 / 100%	120 / 100%	105 / 100%	92 / 100%	39 / 100%	97 / 100%	48 / 100%	1151 / 100%

The table is filled out based on the research conducted by the authors

Fig. 2. Map of the lexical-semantic composition of oikonyms of the districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Map created by O.O.Baltabaev.

In the Kegeyli district, the Karakalpak live compactly and have been farming since time immemorial. They live together with their clans in the same villages. They assigned their ancestral names to newly developed lands, newly dug canals and ditches. Moreover, along with clan names, the names of clan leaders were also preserved; some settlements were named in their honour, which led to the emergence of new anthroponyms.

Muynak district is located in the south of the Aral Sea; therefore, there are many villages whose names mainly consist of hydronyms. As a result of the shallowing of the river and a decrease in the sea water level, a number of hydraulic objects have disappeared over the past 50 years.

In the Nukus district there are also many ethnooikonyms and anthroponyms associated with clan leaders, that is, veterans. Since the area is located along the river and the local population is engaged in agriculture, there are many oikonyms in the area, derived from hydronyms.

The Takhiyatas region is also located along the Amudarya River, and there are many oikonyms here, named after canals, lakes and other hydraulic structures. Since Karakalpak, Uzbeks, Kazakhs and Turkmens lived mixed in the region, there were also a large number of ethnooikonyms named after their clans.

Studying its historical maps, we witnessed a huge number of lakes and hydroelectric objects in the Takhtakupir district. Today's oikonyms, such as Balkeuzek, Pishenkul, Shogirkul, Karabayli and Kungradkul, were the names of lakes that once existed. Since

Karakalpak and Kazakh clans have lived in the region in separate groups since ancient times, this circumstance led to the emergence of many ethnooikonyms.

There are many modern (standard) toponyms in the territory of Turtkul district. Because most of the population lives in settlements located on newly developed lands. In addition, there are also many oikonyms named after water bodies.

The location of the Khodjeyli district along the Amudarya River predetermined the spread of a huge number of hydraulic structures, and this, in turn, served as the basis for the appearance of oikonyms based on hydronyms. The region is inhabited by Karakalpaks, Uzbeks, Kazakhs and Turkmens, which is accordingly reflected in the oikonyms.

Chimbay district is one of the territories where Karakalpaks live most densely. From a lexical-semantic point of view, there is the largest number of ethnooikonyms based on purely Karakalpak clan names. It should be noted that there are also many oikonyms in the area, named after the historical leaders of clans.

As for the Shumanay district, the main part of oikonyms consists of modern (standard) names. The population's tradition of irrigation farming served as the basis for the spread of oikonyms derived from the names of canals.

In contrast, in the Ellikkala district modern (standard) oikonyms make up the majority. Although some oikonyms bear the names of historical figures such as Abay, Berdakh, Beruni and Ulugbek, in some areas bordering the north of Kyzylkum, oikonyms bear the names of ethnic Kazakh farmers, as a result, this caused the spread of anthropooikonyms in the area.

The fact that the Karakalpaks, Kazakhs, and Uzbeks lived in the territory of the Kanlikul district as a tribe is reflected in the ethnooikonyms of the district. We can also observe many oikonyms, formed mainly from the names of ditches and canals, common in the district.

The oikonyms of the Karauzyak district mainly consist of Karakalpak ethnooikonyms. Because this area is one of the territories of compact settlement of the Karakalpaks. From oikonyms based on hydronyms, we can understand that people lived mainly along canals and lakes.

Many oikonyms in the Kungrad district consist of modern (standard) names. However, the ethnooikonyms of the region have long been composed of Karakalpak, Uzbek and Kazakh tribal names.

Conclusion. The results of the study indicate that the oikonymy of the Republic of Karakalpakstan as a whole, including all oikonyms, and the lexical and semantic composition of oikonymy have not yet been studied. In addition, the regional features of the republic's oikonymy have not been determined. In particular, the most oikonyms and ethnooikonyms are found in the Amudarya district, while in Bozatau, Muynak and Takhtakupir districts there are more oikonyms formed from hydronyms. Since they are located in the south of the Aral Sea and there were many lakes and streams, people most often used water bodies to determine the location of villages, i.e. the rural fortresses were named after the nearest hydronyms. Nowadays, most of these lakes and streams have disappeared, but the names of the villages serve as a source or a kind of "sign" indicating the historical hydrography of this area. In Nukus, Kegeyli, Chimbay and Karauzyak districts ethnooikonyms make up the majority, because it is known from history that Karakalpak clans and tribes usually lived along channels and canals. As for the Beruni, Turtkul, Ellikkala, Shumanay and Kungrad districts, modern (standard) names predominate here, since in these areas most of the settlements were founded in Soviet times on newly developed lands. Therefore, they were named in accordance with Soviet ideology. Later, after Independence, they were renamed according to government decrees. In the Khodjeyli, Takhiyatas and Kanlikul districts, the number of oikonyms, ethnooikonyms and anthropooikonyms formed from hydronyms is close to each other, none of them has a complete predominance over the others in number.

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